

УДК 130.2

**PEDAGOGICAL MYTHMAKING AND
CONSTRUCTION OF NEW EDUCATIONAL REALITY**

O. Razumenko, doctoral student of philosophy Kharkiv
National Pedagogical University G.Skovoroda

It was shown that modernization of Ukrainian society requires understanding of the need to activate human potential as an essential resource for preserving and developing modern civilization. Primarily, it refers to the educational system, which is a leading social institution in forming intellectual potential of the country. In the modern society the function of an educational establishment is not limited to fulfilling the social order. Instead, contemporary educational must, first of all, ensure consistency in implementing innovations. Therewith, an educational establishment must have the teaching staff ready to productive activities.

Key words: teacher, educational reality, pedagogical mythmaking, educational system.

Currently a range of traditional requirements (ability to design pedagogical process, organize cooperation, operatively control work progress, make adjustments and corrections, thoroughly analyze achievements, find reasons of failures and shortages and, finally, arrange the process on the level that enables to achieve the goals) is complemented with a number of innovations. They include the need to implement dynamic educational strategies and pedagogical relations that continuously regenerate, develop adaptation mechanisms and practical means of reviewing conventional definitions where oppositions disappear not by removing them, but by uniting, complementing and converging. It is to be noted that globalisation deploys educational process on the level of comprehensive understanding of a human and humanity, humanism and fundamental values supported by the past, present and future [2, c. 23]. Consequently, there emerge new requirements to the teacher's professional competence.

The processes of education modernization in effect involve the core streams in the development of modern educational establishments. Rigid monotony has been replaced by the ideas of humanization, competency approach, student-centred education, differentiation and integration of educational process, freedom of choice in the content and forms of educational activities, models of educational establishments.

Social relations in forming the educational field can be differentiated. There it is possible to single out the relation, clearly determining the rights and responsibilities of each subject in interaction (a teacher, a student, parents). The interaction has become more regulated (standardized), and further controlled. As a result, person's behaviour in education has become more predictable, and the institution activities promote self-renovation.

An educational establishment as an institutional form or organization in the system of education preserves this core feature. It means that today the main direction in the growth and development of any educational establishment is creating preconditions for student's cultural development and forming cultural environment.

The idea of forming the cultural educational field as a precondition for individual studying and educating is naturally determined. School new objectives, the variety of educational establishments, curricula, educational materials, sociocultural processes, related to humanization, humanitarization, expansion of information field are also the factors, which should be taken into account when organizing the field. At the same time, it appears that the cultural and educational field cannot be clearly and accurately outlined since it obviously has high level of uncertainty and ambiguity: it a priori should be excessive and multi-optional, which provides ensures free development, and thus implementation of humanistic education and teaching.

It should be mentioned that the cultural and educational field as the total of values and patterns for successful solving any issues faced in life, serves a source of personal development. It is a specifically organized sociocultural and pedagogical environment, which stimulates the development and self-development of each individual involved. This is a system of conditions for the personal and creative children's and teachers' development – all subjects of education. This is the environment of personal development and education. For instance, M. Berdyaev wrote that the solar brightness had to be inside the person as the centre of the universe, and the person must be the sun to be orbited by the others [1, 175].

Therefore, being the integral unity, the cultural and educational field comprises educational and developing environment and extra-curricular entertaining and developing environment.

The educational and developing environment (educational activity, doing home assignments, self-study etc.) is the main source of cognitive cultural

information. The extra-curricular entertaining and developing environment is quite appealing. This is the environment where people can creatively work in teams, where they can communicate, taking advantage of their creative potential in various clubs and associations.

These components of the cultural and educational field are pedagogically arranged environments. These components are influenced by leisure environment, represented by extra-curricular institutions; popular communication environment (mass communication environment); family environment; peer environment; cultural creative environment of educational institutions etc. Nevertheless, they are also pedagogically unarranged environments, which freely emerge and develop, creating the field of information communication. Understanding cultural and educational field as integrity, it is evident that this is a model that consists of specific elements.

Space and semantic element includes architectural-aesthetic organization of educational entities living space (design of educational establishments, interior design etc.) and the symbolic space (various symbols, wall information).

Content and methodological element consists of the concepts of education, teaching, curricula, plans, textbooks etc.; forms and methods of education organization (a lesson, a didactic game, a tour; students' research communities, class structures and students' self-governance etc.).

The communication and organizational element is understood as the specific features of educational entity environments – distribution of statuses, roles, nationalities, gender distribution of students, teachers, their values, beliefs, stereotypes; communication area – the style of communicating and teaching, space and social density of educational entity environment, crowd level; organizational environment – availability of teachers' creative groups, parents' initiative groups etc.

The model presentation of cultural and educational space enables to identify the main fields for its design, development and management: the development of the object-space school environment as a developing environment; the content and organization of educational space (knowledge and science-driven), the development of interpersonal qualities, relations, culture of communication (communication organization, teaching communication and relation management skills).

Paying attention to the cultural and educational field it is to be indicated that provided the formation of the knowledge society, education turns into a

major sociocultural factor, which, in turn, requires précising prospects of the modern education and substantiation of the strategy of updating its content, forms, methods and techniques.

Thus, the knowledge society, which is being currently formed and becomes more and more notable in our country, provides for structuring the new educational universe where pedagogical relations gain new meanings, and play a decisive part in activating anti-crisis potential of education.

The specifics of teaching activity determines the need to use this type of interaction. However, continuous interference with the subject's world may lead to conflict situations, complicating relations between a teacher and students. Therefore, in some cases it is more efficient and effective to apply indirect influence, whose idea is that the teacher puts all his or her efforts not on the individual, but on his or her environment (classmates, groupmates, friends). Changing life conditions, the teacher makes changes in the preferred direction for the subject too. This indirect interaction is more frequently used when working with teenagers, who tend to form their subculture.

While influencing the environment it is justified to use the technique of influence via a reference person. Each student has classmates, whose opinion he or she respects and accepts. These are reference persons for the subject, via whom the teacher organizes influence, making them teacher's allies.

Pedagogical relations are twofold: functional role and personality. In other words, while interacting, the teacher and students perceive the process, on the one hand, as functions and roles of each other, on the other, – individual, personal specific features.

Teacher's personal and role settings can be found in his or her behavior, but the predominance and imbalance entails respective effects in the impact of his or her personality on the student.

The functional role side of the interaction between the teacher and the student is determined by objective conditions of educational process, e.g. student's assessment and performance control. In this case teacher's personality should be beyond the interaction framework.

The optimal suitable option for the educational process is teacher's setting to to carry out functional role and personal interaction, when his or her personal features may be found through role playing behavior. This combination ensures the transmission of not merely general social but also teacher's personal individual experience. Therewith, the teacher, when interacting with the student,

shows and transfers his or her individuality, meeting the need and ability to be a personality and, consequently, forming this need and ability in the student. Nonetheless, practice shows that this setting is used only by those teachers who have highly developed motivational and value-oriented attitude to teaching.

The functional role side of pedagogical interaction is mainly oriented on transforming students' cognitive world. The criterion for teacher's successful activity in this case is the assessment of students' achievements against references given. Teachers who are oriented on this type of interaction seem to fit behavior to the established standards.

The personal side of the pedagogical interaction is more related to the individual's motivations and senses. Scientific knowledge and the content of education are here the means of transforming this area.

Teacher's influence on a person may be voluntary and involuntary. In the former case, it is programmed deliberately, when the teacher simulates and plans expected changes in advance. The teacher, deliberately or non-deliberately offering samples of his/her subject features to other people, first of all students, becomes a role model, finding succession in others. If the teacher is not a reference person to their students, then his/her influence does not properly appeal to them despite highly developed personal, individual and functional role parameters.

Mechanisms of voluntary impact are persuasion and inspiration. Persuasion is a technique of conscious formulation of needs, which encourage a person to act according to values and life standards socially accepted and promoted in the social group.

Persuasion is a system of logical arguments that requires conscious attitude from the recipient. Inspiration, conversely, is based on non-critical perception and allows for affected person's inability to consciously control the inflow of information.

The mandatory pre-condition of any influence is teacher's authority, trust to his or her information, no resistance to his or her influence. Therefore, teacher's rules, thoughts and requirements may become active means of providing significant impact on students' perception and understanding of information.

The specific feature of inspiring is its orientation not on person's logic and reason, not on the readiness to think and consider but rather on receiving orders and instructions. The settings inspired by teacher's authority can become the

platform for assessment to be given by students to each other. In teaching inspiration must be used very cautiously. It may involve and activate motivational, cognitive and emotional aspects of personality.

Inspiring is closely related to following. Following is copying and reproducing actions, deeds, intentions, thoughts and feelings. It is important that a student, following somebody, should realize that his or her actions and thoughts are derived from teachers ones. However, following is not absolute imitating and copying. Role models and references given by the teacher interact with student's personal features.

Following includes identification and generalization. The generalized following is not absolute reproduction of a model, example, it encourages similar actions, but with specific quality features. Under this following only general ideas are borrowed. It requires much more quick thinking and smartness, most often related to individual and creative work, being its initial stage. With time personality develops, thus giving a spur for independence and suppressing following.

In addition, it is to be noted that the category of pedagogical interaction takes into account personal features of the subjects of interaction and ensures acquisition of social skills, and mutual transformation based on trust, creativity, parity and cooperation.

References

1. Бердяев Н.А. Человек. Микрокосм или макрокосм / Русский космизм: Антология философской мысли. М.: Педагогика - Пресс, 1993. – С. 171 – 175.
2. Філософія як теорія і методологія розвитку освіти / Філософія освіти ХХІ століття: проблеми і перспективи. Збірник наукових праць. Вип. 3. - К.: Знання, 2000. – С. 17 – 23.

ПЕДАГОГИКА МИФОТВОРЧЕСТВА И СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВО НОВОЙ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ РЕАЛЬНОСТИ

О. Разуменко

В статье показано, что модернизация украинского общества требует понимания необходимости активизации человеческого потенциала в качестве важного ресурса для сохранения и развития современной цивилизации. В первую очередь, это относится к системе образования, которая является ведущим социальным институтом в формировании интеллектуального потенциала страны. В современном обществе функции образовательного учреждения не ограничиваются выполнением общественного порядка. Вместо

этого, современные образовательные системы должны, прежде всего, обеспечить согласованность внедрения инноваций. При этом, учебное заведение должно иметь преподавательский состав готовый к новаторской производственной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: учитель, образовательная реальность, педагогическая мифотворчества, система образования.

ПЕДАГОГІКА МІФОТВОРЧОСТІ І БУДІВНИЦТВО НОВОЇ ОСВІТНЬОЇ РЕАЛЬНОСТІ

О. Разуменко

У статті доведено, що модернізація українського суспільства вимагає усвідомлення потреб актуалізації людського потенціалу як важливішого ресурсу збереження та розвитку сучасної цивілізації. В першу чергу це відноситься до системи освіти, яка є провідним соціальним інститутом у формуванні інтелектуального потенціалу країни. В сучасному суспільстві функція освітньої установи не обмежується тільки виконанням соціального заказу. Сучасна освіта, перш за все, повинна забезпечувати ціленаправлене здійснення інноваційних перетворень. При цьому освітня установа повинна мати педагога, який був би готовий до продуктивної діяльності.

Ключові слова: педагог, освітня реальність, педагогічна мифотворчість, система освіти.